

THE EFFECT OF THERMAL RESISTANCE ON THE CURING PROCESS OF A COMPOSITE PART

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Abstract: The quality of composite parts is highly depended on the cross-linking reaction of polymer matrix which controlled by the temperature in the curing process. Based on the experiments of manufacturing for a composite part, it was found that both of the auxiliary materials packaged in vacuum bag and the contact faces between the molds and composite part would induce a non-negligible thermal resistance effect which disturbed the temperature distribution in the composite part. An improved finite element model considering the thermal resistance effect was proposed by defining a dynamic thermal contact conductance parameter between the contact faces. Contrast to the experiment results, it illustrates that the improved finite element model would predict more accuracy results than the conventional model and without increasing the computing resource.

1 Introduction

Generally, a high quality composite part produced by prepregs with specific number of plies and ply orientations would experience a curing process in an autoclave. In the curing process, heat and pressure are simultaneously applied to the composite part which initiates an exothermic chemical reaction and squeezes the air and excess resin out of the part. The proper control of the applied heat and pressure, i.e. the cure cycle, is critical to produce a high quality composite part where the resin is evenly distributed, forms a void-free continuous phase saturating the fibers, and is completely cured [1].

The conventional cure cycle recommended by the prepregs supplier is usually successful for manufacturing of thin flat laminates. However, studies have shown that the conventional cure cycle

can result in extremely temperature distribution at the composite part with complex shape in the curing process due to the distinct boundary conditions and this can cause matrix cured non-uniform and thermal residual stress.

In the curing process, a composite part with complex shape is placed on a specific mold surface covered by release film, and then the composite part and mold are covered with auxiliary materials such as peel ply, bleeder, caul plate, dam, and vacuum bag. Most of the previous researchers modeled only the composite part and neglect all thermal resistance related to tooling and other auxiliary materials [2], or they performed analysis using the measured surface temperature of composite part [3, 4]. However, the effects of tooling and auxiliary materials cannot be neglected because their thermal resistance properties are dependent on the geometry of the tooling and vacuum bag assembly such as thickness of the tool plate, caul plate, and bleeder layer.

Surfaces that appear to be smooth are actually composed of microscopic asperities and depressions that deviate from an apparently smooth surface. When two surfaces are in contact with each other, the actual area of contact is much smaller than the apparent area of contact. These areas of actual contact occur where the asperities of one surface are in contact with the asperities of the other surface. As the assembly of composite part is covered with a vacuum bag, there are no interstitial materials between the contact areas. Hence, most of the heat transferred across the interface formed by the two surfaces is transferred through these small contact spots. This limited contact area constricts the flow of heat to a few channels at the interface between the materials, making the temperature distribution in the vicinity of the interface complex and three-

dimensional. An approximation to this complex temperature distribution is to assume a temperature discontinuity at the interface, with the associated temperature drop determined by the temperature distribution on either side of the interface. This temperature discontinuity is proportional to the heat flux through the interface, with the proportionality constant called the thermal contact conductance (or thermal contact resistance), and defined in terms of the temperature drop across the interface and the heat flux through the interface [5].

The effect of thermal contact resistance on heat transfer have been widely recognized and researched in design of aerospace industry, electronic packaging and nuclear reactors [6]. There are many experimental data with some correlations were reported for thin metallic members bolted or riveted with air as the interstitial substance. The NASA engineers were concerned with thermal contact resistance at many joints found in spacecraft and satellites which function under vacuum conditions. In the unclear industry, many elaborate and costly in-situ experiments were conducted to measure thermal contact resistance over a range of temperature, contact pressure, and gas pressure. The experimental results were frequently correlated, and a few empirical models were reported. However, the effect of thermal contact resistance on the heat transfer during the curing process of a composite part has not been reported.

The paper focus on the temperature distribution in an assembly of composite part during the curing process, and proposed an improved model which considers the effect of thermal resistance causing by the auxiliary materials and contact faces between the molds and composite part. Based on the experiments, a dynamic thermal contact conductance model defining at the contact faces was proposed. The simulation results show that the temperature variations predicted by the improved model are agreement well with the experimental results.

2 Theories

2.1 Thermal conduct

The temperature profiles in a composite part in the curing process can be obtained through a transient heat transfer analysis including an interior heat source. The combined thermal and cross-linking

reaction in polymer issue for a given temperature cycle is referred to as the primal thermo-chemical analysis. The temperature can be assumed to be in local equilibrium at any time in the prepregs [7]. The transient heat transfer differential equation with an interior heat source for the prepregs in the curing process could be expressed as

$$\rho c \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(k_{ij} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_j} \right) + \dot{Q} \quad (1)$$

where \dot{Q} is the interior heat source ratio, k_{ij} are the composite anisotropic thermal conductivities, ρ and c are composite density and composite specific heat, respectively, and t is the time of thermal conduction. For simplify, the thermal conduction in the curing process for composite part can be simulated by a 2D model, thus the number of parameter k_{ij} would be reduce to 2, i.e. the k_{yy} and k_{zz} .

The interior heat source caused by the cross-linking reaction in polymer can be calculated with a cure law of polymer. It is expressed as

$$\dot{Q} = \rho H_r \frac{d\alpha}{dt} \quad (2)$$

where α is the cure degree of polymer, $d\alpha/dt$ is the rate of cure determined by the cure kinetics of polymer, H_r is the heat of reaction of prepregs, defined as the total amount of heat evolved during a complete polymer reaction.

Based on the phenomenology, the cure kinetics of a polymer system can be described by the Arrhenius equation and the law of cure degree variation [2].

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = K(T) f(\alpha) \quad (3)$$

where $K(T)$ and $f(\alpha)$ are the Arrhenius equation associated with temperature and the law of cure degree variation, respectively. The specific expression of the law of cure degree variation depends on the polymer system.

The cure kinetics for the Glass/Polyester material system can be expressed as

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = A \exp\left(\frac{-\Delta E}{RT}\right) \alpha^m (1-\alpha)^n \quad (4)$$

where A , ΔE , m and n are the constants of polymer properties whose value determined by fitting the experiment data of differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). A is the pre-exponential factor, ΔE is the activation energy; m and n are the exponential factor of curing. R is the universal gas constant, T is the Kelvin temperature.

The cure kinetics for a Carbon/Epoxy material system can be expressed as

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = A \exp\left(\frac{-\Delta E}{RT}\right) (1-\alpha)^n \quad (5)$$

where the parameters of A , ΔE , n , R , T and t are the same to the aforementioned parameters.

To solve the coupling Eq. (1) and (3), the time domain is discretized using the θ method and the thermal properties are assumed constant in each iteration. The solution of cure degree at the next time step using:

$$\alpha^n = \alpha^{n-1} + \left[(1-\theta)\dot{\alpha}^{n-1} + \theta\dot{\alpha}^n \right] \Delta t \quad (6)$$

where α^n and α^{n-1} are the solution at the previous and current time steps respectively; Δt is the time step. The parameter θ is an adjustable parameter varying between 0 and 1 and the algorithm depends on the chosen value of θ . If θ between 0.5 and 1, the integration procedures are known as implicit methods.

Since non-linearity occur from thermal properties and internal heat generation which are dependent on temperature and degree of cure, an iterative procedure is necessary to solve the equations. The Newton-Raphson algorithm, due to its quadratic convergence characteristics, is employed and the tangent stiffness matrix is updated each iteration.

2.2 Thermal contact resistance

There are several theoretical and experimental studies on the thermal contact resistance in the open literature, especially for the contact between conforming rough surfaces [5]. One of the most

accepted theoretical thermal contact resistance models was developed by Cooper, Mikic, and Yovanovich (CMY) for isotropic surfaces deforming plastically. The thermal contact resistance R_m averaged over the contact interface area could be defined by the following equation,

$$R_m = \frac{T_{m1} - T_{m2}}{q_m} \quad (7)$$

where q_m is the mean heat flux, T_{m1} and T_{m2} are the mean temperatures of contact surfaces, respectively, which are evaluated using an extrapolation method of the temperatures sufficiently away from the interface. Figure 1 show the schematic of thermal contact resistance.

Figure 1 Schematic of thermal contact resistance

A thermal contact resistance is associated with the materials, pressure, temperature and roughness of contact surface, and is the reciprocal of thermal conductance [5]. The thermal contact conductance h can be expressed as following

$$h = \sum_{i=0}^N h_i = \sum_{i=0}^N 2a_i \lambda_s \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{3p_i}{4Ea_i b_i}} \right)^{-\frac{3}{2}} \quad (8)$$

$$\lambda_s = \frac{2\lambda_1 \lambda_2}{\lambda_1 + \lambda_2}$$

where h_i is the thermal contact conductance of contact spot i , N is the number of contact spot on surface, a_i and b_i are the radius and curvature of

contact spot i on surface, respectively, p_i is the pressure on contact spot i , E is the effective modulus of contacting bodies defined by Hertz, λ_s is the effective thermal conductivity of contact surface defined by the thermal conductivity of contacting bodies λ_1 and λ_2 . It can be seen that the determination of thermal contact conductance h would be a complex procedure and consume a lot of computing resource while conducting a simulation. However, for simplify, the overall effect of thermal contact resistance would be considered by defining an equivalent thermal contact conductance h_e

$$h_e = \beta_i + \beta_\infty \frac{T - T_0}{T_{\max} - T_0} \quad (9)$$

where β_i and β_∞ are the values of thermal contact conductance at room temperature and cure temperature, respectively.

3 Experiments

Generally, there is a complex geometrical pattern on a composite part such as a grid-stiffened structure which would enhance the advantages of composite laminate by a grid structure. To reduce the cost, the composite part is manufactured by an innovative curing process, i.e. the whole structure would be cured in one manufacture procedure by a rubber mold designed grooves for ribs. The rubber mold would save the time for the procedure of molds assembly and de-mold. Besides, the rubber mold is much easier fabricated and designed than other molds due to the flexibility and thermal mechanical properties. During the curing process, prepregs are laid-up on the rubber mold with desired number and orientation of plies. Once the procedure is finished, the assembly of mold and prepregs are covered with auxiliary materials such as bleeder and breather, and then sealed inside a vacuum bag. The whole assembly is placed in an autoclave and undergoes a prescribed temperature and pressure cycle.

Figure 2. Sketch of the rubber mold

The sketch of the rubber mold is shown in Figure 2, where the rubber is represented by the gray blocks, and the gaps between silicon rubbers represent the grooves for ribs. The prepregs for the composite part is composed by carbon fiber T700 and epoxy resin 603 provided by the Tory Inc. in Japan and the Aerospace Research Institute of Materials & Processing Technology in China, respectively. The prepregs with the stack sequences $[0/90]_{10s}$ for skin and $[0]_{100}$ for ribs, were laid on the rubber mold by the handing lay-up technique, and then assembled with auxiliary materials such as Teflon and bleeder. The assembly was bagged with a vacuum bag (shown in Figure 3), and cured in an autoclave with the cure cycle recommended by the supplier of resin 603, that is, the temperature of air in autoclave was respectively dwelled at 135°C for 1hour and 190°C for 4h with the ratio $25^\circ\text{C}/\text{h}$, and then cooled down to the room temperature with the ratio $-20^\circ\text{C}/\text{h}$. During the curing process, the temperature variation in the prepregs were monitored by two embedded FBG temperature sensors with a diameter 0.8mm, which one was embedded in the center of a cell skin and the other was embedded in the center of a lateral rib. The temperature variation of metal molds was also monitored by an additional FBG temperature sensor placed in the lid-plate surface of the assembly.

a. Sketch of assembly of the prepress

b. Setup for monitoring the temperature variation

Figure 3 Experiment for the curing process of composite part

A composite part was fabricated by the curing process and the monitored results are shown in Figure 4. As the cross-linking reaction of resin 603 would be finished at second dwell period, the monitored results at the cooling down period were not shown. Due to the low thermal conductivities of auxiliary materials and a low elevated rate in cure cycle, the temperature of composite part was increasing gradually without a clear distinction between the elevated periods and the first dwell period. It can be observed that there is a uniform distribution of temperature in it means the cross-linking reaction was moderate. As the temperature of composite part was elevated continually, the cross-linking reaction of resin was intensified and generated a mass of heat which results in the temperature of composite part over the mold temperature. Due to the low thermal conductivity of rubber, a shootover was monitored which happened at the beginning of second dwell period. It can be observed that the temperature difference between skin and rib is over 7°C at the beginning of second dwell period, and reducing while the curing progress.

The monitored results illustrate that there is a uniform temperature field in the composite part, and the composite part could be successfully fabricated by the curing process. Owing to the difference of thermal conductivities between composite and molds, there is distinct temperature distribution in them, i.e. the diversity of temperature is increasing while the curing proceeding. However, the diversity of temperature is decreasing while the composite part has been cured 3 hours. Finally, the diversity of temperature is reversed and increasing continually. It can be concluded that there is an essential thermal contact conductance between the composite part and molds.

Figure 4 Monitoring results in the experiment

4 Numerical simulations

4.1 Model verify

To verify the solution for simulation the heat conduction of composite in the curing process, a 2D finite element model for a cross section of 2.54 cm thickness unidirectional composite plate was constructed. The variations of temperature and cure degree during a curing process were simulated by the model with the material system Glass/Polyester, and the simulation results are shown in Figure 5. According to the Bogetti's work [2], the boundary conditions are that the top and bottom boundary are the convection boundary condition with a coefficient h_r $108.15 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$ while the other boundary are adiabatic due to the symmetry, and the thermal and cure kinetic parameters of the Glass/Polymester are shown in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively. It is seen that the simulation results are agree well with the numerical results obtained by Bogetti, and a shootover is also observed during the second dwell

period of cure cycle when a severe crosslinking reaction happened. It could be concluded that the subroutine could manifest well the variations of temperature and cure degree during the curing process of composites.

Table 1 Thermal parameters of composite and molds

	ρ /(kg/m ³)	C /KJ/(mol·K)	$K/W\cdot(m\cdot K)^{-1}$	
			K_{33}	K_{11}/K_{33}
Rubber	1.23e3	1.53	1.23	1
Steel	7.85e3	0.46	50.24	1
G/P	1.89e3	1.26	2.16e-4	2
C/E	1.52e3	9.42e-1	4.46e-4	10

Figure 5 Simulation results vs. Bogetti's results

Table 2 Cure kinetic parameters

Glass/Polyester		Graphite/Epoxy	
A /min	3.7e22	A /min	7.3e4
ΔE J/mol	1.674e5	ΔE J/mol	59.4e3
m	0.524	H_r J/g	550
n	1.476	n	0.8
H_r J/g	77.5		

4.2 Simulation results

According to the assembly of composite part, a 2D finite element model is developed including the composite part and the primary molds, as shown in Figure 6. Incorporating with the cure kinetics, i.e. an n-order model provided by the manufacturer of resin 603, the temperature variation of the composite part in the curing process was predicted by the model. A total 244 nodes and 185 elements were constructed for the composite part with an 8-node plane element. The thermal and cure kinetic parameters required for the simulations are given in Table 1 and Table 2.

According to the periodical repeat pattern of the specimen, the boundary conditions are that the left and right border are adiabatic and the top and bottom border are the direct boundary condition means been applied the monitored temperature T_{mold} .

Figure 6 Finite element model for the simulation

Figure 7 Simulation results with different TCC parameters

To investigate the effect of thermal contact resistance on the curing behavior of composite part, the simulation with an equivalent thermal contact conductance 1, 10 or 100 was conducted, respectively. The corresponding results are shown in Figure 3.8. It shows that there is a great effect of thermal contact resistance on the curing behavior of composite part, i.e. the simulation result would deviate from the monitoring result while an inappropriate thermal contact conductance was defined. Especially, the deviation would be severe when a low thermal contact conductance is adopted, that is the temperature would be underestimated

before the cross-linking reaction initiated while the temperature would be overestimated when the cross-linking reaction happened. It is because that the higher thermal contact conductance the more amount of heat flux would pass the contact faces, i.e. a higher thermal contact conductance would encourage the cross-linking reaction and dissipate the generated heat by reducing the thermal resistance, while a lower thermal contact conductance would suppress the cross-linking reaction and restrict the generated heat by augment the thermal resistance. With increasing temperature, the expansion rubber mold would apply a gradually increasing contact pressure on the composite part which would reduce the thermal resistance between the contact faces. It implies that defining a dynamic thermal contact conductance between the contact faces would be more reasonable and accuracy than adopting a constant thermal contact conductance while conducting the simulation. According to the experiment, a dynamic thermal contact restraint parameter was defined at the contact faces, and the values of β_i and β_∞ were 10 and 100, respectively.

Figure 8 Simulation results vs. monitoring results

The simulation results for the composite specimen are shown in Figure 8 and Figure 9. It can be seen that the temperature variations in the skin center and the rib center are agreed well with the experimental results.

It illustrates that there is a uniform distribution of cure degree in the composite specimen in the curing process, and the final value is over 0.95. The progress of cure degree certifies that the shootover in the monitored results is caused by the interior heat resource determined by the cross-linking reaction. It

can be conclude that the developed solution can quickly and accurately simulate the curing behaviors of composite part in the curing process.

Figure 9 Variation of cure degree in the specimen

5 Conclusions

Based on the experiment, it can be conclude that the temperature variations of a composite part are effected by the covered auxiliary materials and a thermal resistance effect is observed between the contact faces during the curing process. An improved finite element model taking account of the thermal contact resistance between contact faces was developed and verified by the experiment. Comparing the experimental results with numerical simulation results, it is observed that there is a non-negligible effect of thermal resistance between the contact faces and the predicted results of composite part would be more accurate by defining a dynamic thermal contact conductance parameter between the contact faces. The simulation results imply that the solution would be helpful for improve the accuracy of numerical simulation for composite part manufacturing.

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